

OA eBook Usage (OAeBU) Metadata Community Consultation

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About this Document

This community consultation document reflects issues identified through data ingest and matching processes related to the OAeBU Data Trust project's dashboard pilot partnerships with four global university presses, a commercial press, and a publishing platform. The issues relate to how book metadata is used for the disambiguation of books and linking of their characteristics. Specifically, issues relate to how metadata is used to link specific files and their URLs online to the concept of a specific book, the determination of whether a book is open access, and usage data granularity (e.g. chapter vs book level).

How this document was created

This community consultation was compiled by Curtin University as an output of the OAeBU Data Trust dashboard pilot process. It is being reviewed by representatives of BISG and EDItEUR to ensure alignment with book industry best practice guidance and standards. In addition, comments on this document are requested from the OAeBU project's Standards and Norms Working Group and the Policy Working Group, which includes representatives of Project COUNTER and Crossref among many others.

How to respond to this community consultation

The project team requests that responses and feedback be submitted via this online [questionnaire form](#). Discussion is invited on the OAeBU Data Trust Project's [Technical Norms and Standards Working Group email list](#).

How this community consultation will inform the OAeBU Data Trust effort

After public comment is received, the OAeBU Data Trust project's technical team based at Curtin University, in conjunction with BISG and the project's Technical Advisory Group, will prepare a final version of recommended future actions for the project's Advisory Board and publication in the project's Zenodo community page.

Issues

1.0 Book Work and Product Disambiguation

Disambiguation of Works (i.e. which book is which) remains a challenge, despite being addressed by an existing ONIX best practice recommending [ISTC](#) use to identify works.

"Products are the manifestations of works – abstract entities comprising the intellectual property embodied in a manifestation. Each product manifests a work, and a work may be made manifest in several products. Works are also related to other works: a new work can be derived from an existing work by translation, revision, abridgement, compilation and so on. A third edition is a new work, derived (by revision) from the preceding second edition work, and a translated novel in English is a new work that is derived (by translation) from the original work in another language. ISTCs identify works."

-- ONIX for Books Implementation and Best Practice Guide, Release 3.0 rev 7 ([available here](#))

ONIX is the only data source we have providing metadata across all Data Trust Pilot partners and most book publishers and [ISBN-13](#) is a mandatory identifier for ONIX. ISBN is also provided across all the data sources being collated from partners, and present in other data sources (e.g. Crossref) by most other data providers, most of the time. Other identifiers are less comprehensive or consistent (e.g. DOIs are found in different ONIX fields amongst the project partners and those fields are frequently not populated in the current data) and less consistently applied (and also frequently have complex duplication e.g. DOIs). There are multiple ISBNs for one book-work, however this is a one (work) to many (ISBN) relationship whereas with DOIs for example situations can arise where there are many to many relationships (e.g. multiple DOIs representing chapters and multiple DOIs representing works, with a lack of linking metadata describing relationships).

a. Current OAeBU DT Pilot Approach

In our data systems a Work Family is defined by the collection of ISBNs associated with each other. That is, the collection of ISBNs that are found associated together are collectively used to define the related set of Works. By default we have thus far adopted the book-product, work, and "work family" definitions from ONIX. "Work family" often but not exclusively refers to editions across the pilot data feeds.

b. Longer-term Proposal

- a) Expand and standardise the use of [RelatedWorks](#) and [RelatedProducts](#) ONIX fields as the basis for aggregating metrics to the product and work level
- b) Develop and encourage adoption of improved standard approaches to signal relationships

c. Questions for Community Reflection

1. Given the inconsistent state of current practice, do you agree with the longer-term proposal?
2. Are there other existing standards or efforts working on best practice that should be involved in work to advance the longer-term proposal?
3. How can Crossref information on DOIs be leveraged, noting that this information sometimes (but inconsistently) gives us information at the chapter level (see below on Granularity)?
4. What is the best or consistent practice on handling editions?
 - o ONIX [RelatedProducts](#) with "replaces" or "isReplacedBy" relationships appears to be the best option for linking data

2.0 Open Access (OA) Status

Although not a major issue for the Data Trust Pilot, OA status is an important characteristic of book products. Limited information is available about OA status, and the data is not in any consistent form. Presence of a work in DOAB can indicate OA status (this is true of all books within the Data Trust Pilot), and the development of the OA catalogue by EBSCO parallels this work.

EBSCO supports three methods for publishers to designate OA status in their ONIX 2.1 feeds. Adoption of a standard approach to express OA status in ONIX would allow the Data Trust to obtain this information directly from the existing ONIX ingest process in the future. EBSCO representatives noted that there were significant

issues with elements of the supply chain being incompatible with one or more approaches for some publishers. To quote ...our project's EBSCO communications:

EBSCO can currently support three methods of identifying OA titles in your ONIX 2.1 feed. Please include one or more of the following in each relevant product record:

- Within the `<OtherText>` composite
 - `<TextTypeCode>47</TextTypeCode><Text>Open access - no commercial use</Text>`
- Within the `<SupplyDetail>` composite
 - `<AudienceRestrictionFlag>R</AudienceRestrictionFlag><AudienceRestrictionNote>Open access</AudienceRestrictionNote>`
- Within the `<SupplyDetail>` composite
 - `<DiscountCoded><DiscountCodeType>02</DiscountCodeType><DiscountCodeTypeName>OpenAccessCode</DiscountCodeTypeName><DiscountCode>OA</DiscountCode></DiscountCoded>`

-- EBSCO... (available here)

EDITEUR also [provides guidelines for the use of ONIX 2.1 and 3.0 to convey OA status](#). They propose signalling status through the license element `<EpubLicense>` (only available in ONIX 3.0) and/or through `<TextContent>` (for ONIX 3.0) or `<OtherText>` (for ONIX 2.1). EDITEUR explicitly advises against using pricing information to indicate OA status as a `<PriceAmount>` of 0 is not allowed. The recommend use of the `<UnpricedItemType>` element to specify free of charge

a. Current OAeBU Data Trust Pilot Approach

Our current default is to use presence in DOAB and/or OAPEN as an indicator of OA status. Within the pilot we will seek to report on the presence of other structured information provided by publishers through their ONIX feed but will not rely on it for any analysis.

b. Longer-term Proposal

Consistent with an emphasis on ONIX as the central transmission mechanism for book-related data, develop community standards for expressing OA status and greater consistency on product licensing (including the specifics of copyright licenses) more generally¹.

c. Questions for Community Reflection

1. Do you agree with the longer-term proposal?
2. Are there other existing standards or efforts working on best practice that should be involved in work to advance the longer-term proposal?
3. What is the best mechanism to move this forward?
4. Which socio-political issues surrounding the definition of OA must be addressed for OA Book usage data linking to occur at scale? How should these be addressed?

3.0 Usage Data Reporting Granularity

Books come in pages, chapters, volumes, series and other categories. Broadly speaking in the data trust pilot our working definition of a book is “something that has an ISBN”. The mapping to DOIs is one area where granularity is complex, and many usage data sources have substantially differing approaches to managing both the granularity at which a book is provided, and the way in which usage of those different granularities is reported.

Across ingested pilot partners' usage data, there is currently no usage data that reports consistently at the chapter level; usage is being reported at the product (book) level even when that usage is of chapters in the underlying systems. Given this inconsistency, developing chapter-level data workflows fell outside of the capacity and timeline of the current OAeBU Data Trust pilot dashboards.

¹ While copyright licensing and open access status are sometimes assumed to be synonymous there are a wide range of technical and political issues which make this conflation inadvisable. In particular the need for technical clarity in an area where there is significant contention over policy and legal status means that a separation of concerns is likely to add in practical implementation.

The key to enabling granular usage data reporting appears to require:

- 1) a standardised *mapping* for usage data relevant to a specific level of granularity (e.g. chapter level usage linked to chapters),
- 2) a stable identifier that uniquely represents that specific granular element (e.g. a chapter DOI), and
- 3) a mapping between the stable granular identifier and the work identifier (ISBN).

Crossref's relationship typology may be able to provide this. Equally this could be represented within ONIX [relatedProduct](#) fields. Both of these cases would require the identified element in a usage data source to be a chapter.

a. Current OAeBU Data Trust Pilot Approach

The pilot data trust infrastructure takes data "as is" from data providers. If appropriate given the quality and ambiguity of usage *and* identification data, usage data can then be aggregated to a product and work level. The term "appropriate" is doing a lot of work in that sentence; the mapping of identifiers that may represent products, works or chapters is complex and this occurs both in the book metadata (broadly ONIX and Crossref) feeds and the usage data, where inconsistent or ambiguous identifiers may be used. This will be specific to the combination of input bibliographic metadata (i.e. the publisher) and usage data provider and will be a major theme of ongoing work for the foreseeable future.

b. Longer-term Proposal

We do not currently have a specific proposal beyond an ongoing program of encouraging the greater use and expansion of existing best-practice guidance and standards, the identification of areas where new practices and standards are required, and the implementation of agreed practices and standards. This will be an ongoing area where community discussion and commitment to continuous improvement will be necessary.

c. Questions for Community Reflection

1. What organisations have an interest in increasing the quality and completeness of product-component metadata and identification throughout the supply chain?
2. What existing best practices are available and how can implementation be enhanced?
3. Should the ecosystem and/or data trust recommend DOIs be treated as chapter identifiers (using the [book-chapter type](#) in Crossref as a marker to enable identification)?

4.0 Additional Technical Questions on Metadata Sources

As we develop specific parts of the data integration workflow there are a set of specific questions that arise relating to the use and structure of specific metadata elements.

4.1 Date of Publication

There are several options for "date of publication" in the ONIX data for each work/title, and these dates may differ slightly. Currently these date fields do not appear to be used consistently by different project partners. The choice of date to use as the default publication date will impact on the resulting analyses, filtering, benchmarking *etc.* in the pilot dashboards.

Question for Community Reflection

1. Which ONIX field should we derive the "date of publication" from to be used as the default in our data records?
 - Publication Date
 - Date of First Publication

4.2 Source and format of author names.

There are a number of sources of author names in our data. ONIX [PersonName](#) is the primary field currently being used. However this field is not consistently formatted across the different sources of ONIX data.

Questions for Community Reflection

1. Is ONIX [PersonName](#) an acceptable source of name information for use in the pilot dashboards?

2. If not, or for future development what other sources should be used? In addition to ONIX records, data sources including Microsoft Academic Graph, Crossref, DOAB, and OAPEN have author name fields. These are all publisher-controlled data sources. In addition ORCID provides an author controlled source of preferred name if an ORCID is available from other metadata (e.g. ONIX)
3. Does the format of author names matter? If so, what is your preference for default formatting of author names in data displays?

4.3 Initial source of subject categorisations for benchmarking investigations in the data trust pilot

Individual title data can be grouped/aggregated by subject category data. This is useful for understanding patterns in publication areas and filtering data to a single subject. It is also important for benchmarking publications relative to others in those subject areas.

We currently have a range of data sources for subject categories. None of these subject classifications have complete data coverage, which means that books/works that are not included in a classification will not be included in any resulting aggregations or benchmarks. Mapping from ONIX to any other data source is not complete and therefore selecting any other source will also lead to a loss of coverage:

Question for community reflection

1. Which subject categorisation would you suggest that we focus on initially as a source of information for supporting filtering and benchmarking functionality?
 - BISAC (from ONIX, OAPEN and DOAB- it is unclear if they actually all say the same)
 - BIC (from ONIX, OAPEN and DOAB - it is unclear if they actually all say the same)
 - ONIX Keywords
 - MAG fields of study
 - Crossref subjects
 - Subjects in OAPEN metadata

5.0 How to encourage standards adoption in institutions with limited resources

All of these issues are a bit chicken and egg. There has been substantial work on best practices and standards which is inconsistently implemented. In some cases recommended practices and standards may have been superseded by technical changes or may have not been adopted due to a lack of technical support for implementation in practice, particularly for smaller publishers. In practice there are limited choices for the big options here but lots of issues with details of implementation (e.g. which way to signal OA status).

Many issues stem from a disconnect between technical capacity required to implement standards and the limited resources of small publishers. Many players in the ecosystem do not have full control over their own metadata systems and/or who lack the resources to improve them. As noted in the [OA Books Supply Chain Mapping report](#) there can be a mismatch of incentives between different metadata and service providers in improving metadata quality overall.

A concrete example is the benefits that would arise from a system-wide adoption of ONIX 3.0 over 2.1. However, with many systems providing or dependent on v2.1 questions of how to encourage a system-wide shift will need to be addressed.

Questions for Community Reflection

1. How do we balance the need for some concrete examples for people to see and work from with respect to standards development, with those concrete examples being dependent on making initial decisions?
2. How do we build systems that help small and less well-resourced players adopt and implement standards? How can those smaller players be engaged in the development of widely applied standards with their limited resources and time?